

THE STRUCTURE OF NORMAL WHITE RAT TESTES

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Summary

Testicles of white rats serve as experimental organs to study the pathogenic effect of various chemical or physical factors. Therefore, it is important to know its normative indicators.

Key words: testes, morphology, rats

The testicles are the main male sex organs; its function is not only the production of male sex gametes, but also the synthesis and controlled release of the main androgen (testosterone) [].

They have an oval shape, are located in the scrotum and are separated by a testicular barrier. The size of the testes varies among mammals, but their structure is almost identical in humans and laboratory rodents. Experts compared the testes of several species of lab rats and found no differences in their histology or sperm count.

Inspection methods. For the experiment, 50 3-month-old white male rats kept in standard vivarium conditions were selected. They were quarantined for 2 weeks before the experiment and transferred to other rooms after exclusion of various somatic, infectious diseases. The rats were kept under a 12-hour light regime and provided with sufficient water and 3 meals a day. At the end of the experiment, the rats were euthanized under light ether (chloroform) anesthesia on an empty stomach. Testes were isolated for morphological examination.

Results and conclusions. One of the distinctive features of the standard structure of seminiferous tubules of the control group of rats is characterized by the formation of the hematotesticular barrier by Leydig cells, which are among the many interstitial cells between the seminiferous tubules of the testes, and the inability of any toxic substances to pass through this barrier. Interstitial cells also include fibroblasts, histiocytes and other types of cells, which are important for maintaining fluid balance in the intertubular space. The relative arrangement of histiocytes, fibroblasts and pericytic cells with Leydig cells around the blood vessel plays an important role in ensuring the normal morphofunctional state of the convoluted tubules.

The convoluted tubules are also composed of transitory tubules, which produce spermatogenic cells and transfer them to the next ejaculatory duct. The wall of convoluted tubules consists of structures of basal layer, myoid cells, Sertoli cells and spermatogenic cells of different stages. Sertoli cells with wide cytoplasm and light nuclei are located on the inner surface of the basal layer of the convoluted tubules. Different arrangement of spermatogonial cells along the perimeter of these cell membranes creates a unique cytoarchitectonic picture. Through these changes, the Sertoli cells ensure that the process of spermatogenesis is controlled and stimulated.

References:

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